

ISOLATION, CHARACTERIZATION AND SCREENING OF ACTINOMYCETES FOR
ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES FROM SOILS IN THARAKA NITHI COUNTY.

BY

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THIS RESEARCH PROJECT IS SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
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DEDICATION

I dedicate this Research project to my family and friends to whom without their support and encouragement I wouldn't be able to complete the writing and research of this project.

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

M1 - Luria Bertani agar.

TH - upper farms.

T - lower farms.

Fig - figures

Mm - milimetres

Mcg - micrograms .

ABSTRACT

Actinomycetes are an important class of soil microorganisms. They are predominately found in soil, in the silt of water bodies, in the air and plant remains. They are the most abundant organisms that form thread like filaments in the soil. They grow as hyphae like fungi responsible for the

characteristically “earthy” smell of freshly turned soils. Over twenty genera are found in soil habitats. The main objective of this research is to isolate, identify and enumerate actinomycetes from soils found in Tharaka Nithi County and to find out whether the actinomycetes isolated have antibacterial activity against drug resistant pathogenic bacteria. The study area is found in Central Kenta and was divided into two. 15 samples from the upper area and 15 samples from the lower area. Of the 30 samples collected, 10 composite samples were obtained by mixing 3 soil samples of 1g each to form a composite sample. 1g of the composite sample is taken, serial dilution was carried out upto 10^{-4} . The sample was then inoculated using M1 Agar and incubated for 5 to 7 days at 28°C. Feathery colonies indicate presence of actinomycetes. Pure colonies were obtained then gram staining was carried out and observed under a compound microscope. Actinomycetes are gram positive thread like structures. Secondary metabolites were tested using the agar well and diffusion disc method. Zones of inhibition indicated antimicrobial activity against four clinical isolates of *Candida albicans*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*. Positive control was done using known antibiotics against test microorganisms and zones of inhibition measured. The negative control was done using sterile water and it indicated no zones of inhibition. One way ANOVA was used in data analysis of the colonies found ($F=1.46$, $P=0.2308$) and two way ANOVA at 0.05 limit was used to compare the zones of inhibition of the different isolates against the test organisms ($F =1.15$, $P= 0.33$). These were done using SPSS version 17.0. In Conclusion, the soils in Tharaka Nithi County had actinomycete isolates of different colours with white being dominant. The actinomycetes found in these soils had significant antimicrobial activity against the four clinical test micro organisms. The known antibiotics had different activity rate against the test organisms. The antimicrobial activity of the isolates range from resistant to very susceptible. The test microorganisms also indicated resistance and susceptibility to known antibiotics. This study indicates that further studies on the actinomycetes isolated could bring forth a solution to antibiotic resistance.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background information

Actinomycetes are simple prokaryotic organisms that are gram positive, have a high G-C base composition from 55-75 %, aerobic and are thread forming. The name Actinomycetes is derived from Greek aktis (a ray) and mykes (fungus). Description of actinomycetes began with Ferdinand Cohn in 1875 when he observed a filamentous organism in a concretion from a human lacrimal duct and named it *Streptothrix foersteri*. Later on, C.O. Harz in 1878 named the organism he isolated from a case of bovine lumpy jaw as *Actinomyces bovis*. The most common genus of actinomycetes in soil is *Streptomyces*. *Actinomyces* and *Nocardia* are the other two common genera. Actinomycetes species synthesize numerous natural metabolites with diverse biological activity such as antibiotics (Onaka, H. 2006). Antibiotics of actinomycetes origin exhibit a wide variety of chemical structures including amino glycosides, anthracyclines, nucleosides, peptides, polyenes, actinomycins and tetracycline. Generally, antibiotics are difficult to produce by continuous cultivation of microorganisms. Application of immobilized growing cells overcomes this problem by controlling cultivation conditions. Recently, focus on the use of immobilized cells for producing useful bioactive compounds (Takahashi, Y *et al.*, 2003). The antibiotics are widely produced by fermentation using free cell cultures. Cell immobilization is quite effective especially production of oxytetracycline. This research study compares the efficacy of immobilized and free actinomycetes for their antibiotic production and the antimicrobial properties against pathogens. Majority of antibiotics used in human medicine such as streptomycin, neomycin and erythromycin are obtained from soil actinomycetes (Genilloud, 2017). Apart from antibiotics, they also produce enzymes and vitamins. The smell of freshly turned soil is due to geosmins that are produced by these organisms and move through soils as unseen volatiles (Gerber *et al.*, 1965) Actinomycetes perform functions like phosphate solubilization, siderophore production and Nitrogen fixation.

They are environmental friendly and help maintain the biotic equilibrium through nutrient cycling. Furthermore, they decompose more resistant organic materials such as chitin (Sharma *et al.*, 2011). However, some actinomycetes cause diseases such as actinomycosis in humans. In plants, they cause rot of sweet potatoes.

The problem of antibiotic resistance is an emerging problem in the country and in the world over. This phenomenon occurs when bacteria change in some way that reduces or eliminates the effectiveness of drugs either due to mutations or changes in the environment. The overuse of antibiotics has made resistant bacteria more common.

Tharaka Nithi County is found in the slopes of Mt. Kenya. The area of study is Tunyai close to Mitunguu. The area is a dry area with borderline fertile soils. The area of study is divided into two; the upper area (A) and the lower area (B). The samples were collected from farms where the farmers utilize organic manure from farm yard wastes.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Multiple drug resistance is increasingly becoming common in Kenya and the world. Most bacteria and fungi have become resistant to antibiotics. This problem is going to be difficult to contain unless effective solutions are found quickly. Multiple drug resistance is caused mostly by overuse of antibiotics, poor hygiene practices, mutations caused by environmental changes and misuse of antibiotics. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to determine whether the secondary metabolites produced by the actinomycetes are effective against the multidrug resistant microorganisms.

1.3 JUSTIFICATION

The extent of antibiotic resistance has shown a steady increase. Therefore, this necessitates need to establish whether the bioactive metabolites produced by the actinomycetes isolated are effective against these drug resistant microorganisms. This knowledge provides a solution to one of

emerging world problems and is a field that could be further explored for effective treatment of diseases.

1.4 HYPOTHESIS

- I. Soils in Tharaka Nithi County have actinomycetes
- II. Actinomycetes found in soils in Tharaka Nithi County differ morphologically.
- III. Actinomycetes isolated from soils in Tharaka Nithi County have antimicrobial properties.

1.5 OBJECTIVES

1.5.1 General objective

To Isolate and characterize actinomycetes and determine antimicrobial properties of the actinomycetes from soils in Tharaka Nithi County.

1.5.2 Specific objectives;

- i. To isolate and enumerate the actinomycetes from soil samples obtained from Tharaka Nithi County.
- ii. To characterize morphologically the actinomycetes found in soils from Tharaka Nithi County.
- iii. To determine whether the actinomycetes isolated from the soil have antimicrobial properties.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Previous projects on actinomycetes notably (Bizuye *et al.*, 2017) have been carried out from different regions of the country with different soil conditions. The above project was carried out in Juja, Kenya. It is clear that antibiotic resistance is a major problem in which researchers are

collaborating to find solutions against. The soil conditions could have an effect on the growth of actinomycetes present in the soil. In previous studies where actinomycetes were isolated and screened, most of the data was statistically significant and offered promise to the problem of multidrug resistance. This research seeks to contribute to this course of combatting multidrug resistance by investigating whether the soil actinomycetes found in Tharaka Nithi County have significant effect against the bacterial and fungal isolates. The experiment follows procedures previously used in isolation and screening of actinomycetes.

2.2 History of antibiotics discovery

Antibiotics have been in use since time immemorial to treat infections. Various moulds and plant extracts were used to treat infections by some of the earliest civilizations such as the ancient Egyptians who applied mouldy bread to infected wounds. In the late 19th century, scientists began to observe antibacterial chemicals in action. According to White (2012) Paul Ehrlich, a German physician, noted that certain chemical dyes colored some bacterial cells but not others. He concluded that, it must be possible to create substances that can kill certain bacteria without harming other cells. In 1909, he discovered that a chemical called arsphenamine was an effective treatment for syphilis. The word ‘antibiotic’ was coined by the Ukrainian-American scientist Selman Waksman who discovered over 20 antibiotics in his lifetime.

Alexander Fleming, accidentally discovered Penicillin in 1928. He noticed that a fungus, *Penicillium notatum* had contaminated a culture plate of *staphylococcus* bacteria. The fungus had created bacteria free zones wherever it grew on plates. Fleming isolated and grew the mould in pure cultures. He found that *p. notatum* proved extremely effective even at very low concentrations and was less toxic than the disinfectants used at the time (Jamdhade, 2019). During world war, it

was widely used to treat troops for infections in both the field and in hospitals. It was nicknamed the ‘wonder drug’.

2.3 Antibiotics and actinomycetes

An antibiotic is any chemical of natural origin which has effect to kill or inhibit the growth of other types of cells. Antibiotics are low molecular weight molecules produced as secondary metabolites mainly by microorganisms that live in the soil (Chaudhary *et al.*, 2013). Most of these microorganisms form some type of spore or other dormant cell and then antibiotic production happens during sporulation. The table below highlights the antibiotic, their mode of action and their actinomycetes source (Mahajan *et al.*, 2012).

Antibiotic	Microbial source	Action against	Mechanism of action
Streptomycin	<i>Streptomyces griseus</i>	Gram positive and gram negative bacteria	Inhibit protein synthesis
Chloromycetin	<i>Streptomyces venezuelae</i> , <i>S. lavendulae</i>	Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria	Inhibit protein synthesis
Tetracyclin	<i>Streptomyces auerofaciens</i>	Gram positive, Gram negative bacteria and Rickettsia	Inhibit protein synthesis

Oxytetracycline	<i>Streptomyces rimousus</i>	Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria	Inhibit translation
Erythromycin	<i>Streptomyces erythreus</i>	Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria	Inhibit protein synthesis
Amphotericin	<i>Streptomyces nodosus</i>	Fungi	Inactivates membranes containing sterols
Nystatin	<i>Streptomyces noursei</i>	Fungi especially Candida	Inactivates membranes containing sterols

Table 1.1: Antibiotics, their sources and their mode of action.

2.4 Actinomycosis

It's a chronic suppurative, granulomatous disease that affects abdominal, cervical, facial and thoracic areas. The most common cause is *Actinomyces israeli*. This organism affects both man and animals. In cattle it causes a lumpy jaw because a huge tumor is formed in the angle of the jaw (Masand, *et al.*, 2015). In man, the organism forms normal flora and can be isolated from the mouth of a healthy person. Frequently, the infected patient has a tooth extraction and the endogenous organism is established as a traumatized tissue causing a suppurative infection. This infection may also establish itself in the thoracic area. The patient usually has pus. It causes abscess

formation, tissue fibrosis and draining sinuses (Smego Jr, *et al.*, 1998). Diagnosis can be done by obtaining the pus in vial and rotating it where one can see yellow sulphur granules. These granules can also be seen by running sterile water over lesion, the water will wash away the purulent material leaving golden granules. The granules can histologically be seen as surrounded by polymorphonuclei cells. When cultured under anaerobic conditions, microscopic examination will observe gram positive rods with branches. Treatment is through use of antibiotics and in most cases penicillin (Nichols, *et al.*, 1948).

2.5 The characteristics of actinomycetes

The actinomycetes are a group of gram-positive bacteria which form branched filamentous hyphae that resemble fungal hyphae. Their hyphae are approximately 1 μm whereas fungal hyphae are 5 to 10 μm . Their reproduction is asexual using spores known as conidia when they are naked or by sporangiospores if they are enclosed (Marshall *et al.*, 1960). These spores are resistant to desiccation. They are saprophytic and chemoorganotrophic. They produce antibiotics, decompose dead organic material through excretion of extra cellular enzymes which lyse bacteria and keep the bacterial population in check and thus maintain the microbial equilibrium of the soil. They resemble fungi in the hyphal structures and bacteria in hyphal diameter and composition of the cell wall.

2.5.1 Importance of Actinomycetes

The Actinomycetes, forming soil microflora have gained the greatest importance in recent years as producers of therapeutic substances. Many of the Actinomycetes have the ability to produce antibiotics through synthesis of metabolites which hinder the growth of bacteria and some fungi.

The past decade has seen considerable interest in the Actinomycetes as producers of antibiotic substances with a lot of success achieved in therapeutic use of streptomycin, chloromphenicol, aureomycin and tetracycline all of which are metabolites of actinomycetes. Their usefulness is not limited to antibiotic production, they also aid in degradation of organic plant material, lignin and chitin thus their importance in compost formation. Certain species are commensal in the skin flora, oral flora, gut flora and vaginal flora of humans and livestock where they prevent infections by secondary bacteria and fungi.

2.5.2 Distribution and Mode of Nutrition of Actinomycetes

The Actinomycetes are essentially mesophilic and aerobic in their requirements for growth at temperatures of about 28°C. The majority of these are soil organisms and are associated with rotting material. The characteristic odour of soil after it is ploughed or wetted by rain is largely due to the presence of the actinomycetes which contain geosmins. The actinomycetes grow slowly taking about 5-7 days and on artificial media produce hard and feathery colonies which smell decaying leaves or musty earth. They are particularly abundant in forest soil because of the abundance of organic matter. They occur mainly in soils of neutral pH, although some prefer acidic or alkaline soil. They also appear to be tolerant to low water content as compared to other bacteria. The actinomycetes are capable of utilizing a large number of carbohydrates as energy sources when the carbohydrates are present in the media as sole sources of carbon. Most of the Actinomycetes are quire proteolytic and attack proteins and polypeptides, and are also able to utilize nitrates and ammonia as sources of nitrogen. Nearly all synthesize vitamin B₁₂ when grown on media containing cobalt salts, and many are able to synthesize rather complex organic molecules which have antibiotic properties.

2.5.3 Somatic Structures of Actinomycetes

Most of the Actinomycetes are mycelioid. Their development begins as unicellular organisms but grow into branched filaments or hyphae which grow profusely by producing further branches constituting the mycelium. The width of the hyphae is usually 1 μm . The delicate mycelia often grow in all directions from a central point and produce an appearance that has been compared with the rays of sun or of a star hence the name 'ray fungi'. They are Gram-positive. The protoplasm of the young hyphae appears to be undifferentiated, but the older parts of the mycelium show definite granules, vacuoles and nuclei. Many actinomycetes at first produce a very delicate, widely branched, mycelium that may embed itself into the soil, or, if grown in culture, into the solid medium. This kind of mycelium is therefore called the primary mycelium'. After a period of growth, hyphae of a different kind develop, which raise themselves up from the substratum mycelium and grow into the air. These are called aerial hyphae, and the corresponding mycelium is the aerial or secondary mycelium. The aerial mycelium may be white yellow, violet, red, blue, green, or grey and many form pigments that are excreted into the medium. The aerial mycelium is usually slightly wider than the substratum mycelium. The aerial hyphae possess an extra cell wall layer known as the sheath. The hyphal tip undergoes septation within this sheath to form a chain of conidia. Conidial cell contains a plump, deeply staining, oval or rod-shaped nuclear body.

2.5.4 Reproduction in Actinomycetes

Most species reproduce by conidia which are developed in chains from the aerial hyphae. The chains may be straight, flexuous or coiled slightly or extensively. The conidia bearing filaments

are often spirally twisted. Either the whole length of the aerial hypha or only its upper part is transformed into conidia. Each conidium has a roundish nucleus and is surrounded by a firm outer wall. The conidial wall may be smooth, warty, spiny, or hairy. The conidia can survive desiccation for many years. Even the vegetative forms of the Actinomycetes are quite hardy and very adaptable to the varying soil conditions. The conidia appear as a fine powdery coat on the surface of cultures. When the conidia have been scattered on the ground and conditions are favorable they germinate producing one to three or even occasionally four little germ tubes which give rise to mycelioid condition. The primary mycelium in some species commonly breaks up into small fragments called arthrospores, which often look like bacterial cells and which might easily be mistaken for the latter.

2.6 Antibiotic resistance

Antibiotic resistance is slowly becoming a world menace. According to McArthur *et al.* (2013) More than 70% of the human pathogens are resistant to at least one of the drugs previously used to treat it. In cases of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* multiple cases of resistance have occurred repeatedly. Bacterial resistance is attributed to; the drug not reaching its site of action (Chopra *et al.*, 1996). . The drugs might fail to reach its site of action because of mutation in the transport chain where the target protein changes its structure and can no longer bind to the drug. Beta-lactamase concentration between the inner and outer membrane in the periplasmic space that creates an enzymatic barrier. If the drug is a good substrate for β lactamase, it will be destroyed rapidly although the outer membrane could be permeable to the drug. A slow drug entry rate, an inefficient β lactamase and low binding affinity of the drug to the target protein contributes to resistance. Drug inactivation can occur due to production of aminoglycoside-modifying enzyme whose variation of this mechanism failure of the bacterial cell wall to activate a pro-drug causes resistance especially to aminoglycoside antibiotics. In the case of target alteration, it can occur due

to mutation or resistant gene transfer. Other factors that favor drug resistance include; production of enzymes that destroy the chemical structure of drugs, cell wall permeability to the drugs is altered, development of an altered structure of the target to the drug and development of an alternative metabolic pathway.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study location

The soil samples were obtained from farms in Tunyai near Mitunguu in Tharaka Nithi county (S 0°9'35" E 37°49'30"; S 0°9'31" E 37°50'40" ; S 0°9'39" E 37°50'41"; S 0°10'11' E 37°49'21") which were randomly selected. The farms were divided into two regions; the upper and lower region separated by a road. The experiment was done at Kenyatta University laboratories.

Figure 3.1: Map of Tharaka Nithi County

3.2 Experimental techniques and procedures

The design used in this research is an experimental.

3.2.1 Soil sampling

Ten farms at approximately 200m apart were identified for the collection of the soil samples. The soil samples were collected from 10 points across and diagonally in every farm at an interval radius of 5-20 meters using soil auger. The soil auger was sterilized with 70% ethanol between sampling points to avoid cross contamination. Five soil sub-samples were separately obtained, at a depth of 0-30cm following the clearance of organic matter from the soil at each sampling point. The five separately obtained soil sub samples were then homogenously mixed to constitute a composite sample from which 1500g of soil was taken. The soils were separately packed in khaki bags and

double sealed. The soil samples were then transported to Kenyatta University, Microbiology laboratory where analyses were carried out. Soil samples that were not used immediately were stored in a refrigerator at a temperature of 4°C.

3.2.2 Isolation and identification of actinomycetes from soils

The soil samples used were 30; 15 from the upper farms and 15 from the lower farms. 3 samples of 1g each were mixed to obtain 5 composite samples each weighing 3g from the two regions according to their numbers. The total number of samples were 10.

From each of the composite samples, 1g of the soil sample is separately added to a test tube containing 9ml normal saline and shaken vigorously. By use of a micropipette, 1ml aliquot from the stock solution is transferred to another test tube. Serial dilutions of up to 10^{-4} is done. After serial dilutions, 0.1 ml of each sample is plated separately using spread plate technique on M1 agar at 28°C for 5 days. The colonies are then observed, and enumerated against light. Streak plate technique is used to obtain pure colonies.

3.2.3 Gram staining

The isolated actinomycetes are separately placed on glass slides containing a drop of water using a wire loop. The slides are flooded with Crystal violet and allowed to stand for 2 minutes. The excess stain is drained off using running water. Iodine is then used to flood the slides and allowed to stand for 2 minutes. Ethyl alcohol which is a decolourizer is added drop wise and later washed off with running water. Safranin is added as a counter stain for 1 minute and the excess washed off with running water. The slide is dried using blotting paper.

The culture is viewed under a microscope X 40 using oil immersion.

3.3 Biochemical tests

3.3.1 Starch hydrolysis

The actinomycetes plates were incubated at 28°C for 7 days. Gram's iodine was added to the agar plate. The zones of the plate that appeared clear indicated starch hydrolysis.

3.4 Testing for antimicrobial properties

Once the cultures are confirmed to be actinomycetes under the microscope, they are inoculated in nutrient broth and placed in an orbital shaker for two weeks to allow for maturation and production of secondary metabolites. After one week, centrifuging is done to concentrate the metabolites. The supernatant is obtained and the pellets discarded. The obtained supernatant is inoculated on media plates containing the test organisms; *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Candida albicans* that have been swabbed ; by poking holes using a cork borer of 6 µm together with filter disks soaked in the supernatant and allowed to air dry. The zone of inhibition is measured. The negative control is done using sterile water on the filter disks. The positive control is done using known antibiotics and inhibition zones measured. The metabolites are screened again after one week.

3.5 DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis was done using SPSS version 17.0. The colony counts between the upper and lower farms were compared using one way ANOVA. The zones of inhibition and the colonies against the test isolates were compared using Two way ANOVA. The data was fed on Microsoft Excel and graphs generated. Later on, I did an analysis using python: the repository can be found here: https://github.com/Amimo-cell/datascience/blob/main/Actinomycetes_One_way_ANOVA.ipynb

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS

The cultures were done in triplicates. The farms were divided into two. Upper farms are represented as TH and lower farms as T.

Upper and Lower farms	Means of colonies +- standard error
T1	6.67 +- 0.88 ^a
T2	9.00+- 0.00 ^a
T3	8.67+- 2.90 ^a
T4	6.67+-0.67 ^a
T5	5.33+-0.88 ^a
TH1	7.33+-0.33 ^a
TH2	6.00+-0.58 ^a
TH3	6.67+-0.88 ^a
TH4	6.00+-1.53 ^a
TH5	4.00+-1.00 ^a

Table 4.1: colonies of upper and lower farms. F value ((1.46), P value (0.2308).

Means with the same letter are not significantly different.

Physical characterization

Out of the cultures enumerated, 8 were picked for screening of secondary metabolites. Most were from isolates picked from lower farms and they were of different colors.

CHARACTER	RESULTS	STRAIN

Gram staining	Positive	T1, T5a, Th4, T2b, T5b, T4a, T1y, T1w
Motility	Non-motile	T1, T5a, Th4, T5b, T4a, T1y, T2b, T1w
Colony appearance	Cottony	T1, T5a, Th4, T5b, T2b, T4a T1y, T1w
Colony color	White Yellow Pink	T1w, T5a, Th4, T5b, T2b, T1y T4a, T1
Starch hydrolysis	Positive	T1, Th4, T2b, T5b, T5a, T4a, T1y, T1w

Table 4.2: Morphological characterization of the study isolates obtained from soils.

Plate1: Culture of Actinomycetes on M1 media at 28°C for 5-7 days

Plate 1: Pure culture of Actinomycetes streaked on M1 media at 28°C for 5-7 days

The actinomycetes are grown on M1 media at 28°C and had different colors. Pure colonies are obtained through streaking on M1 media.

Figure 4.1: Actinomycetes under a light microscope

The actinomycetes are gram positive and appear thread like. Long rods are also picked as actinomycetes unlike *Bacillus*. They were viewed using oil immersion at X40.

Plate 3: Starch hydrolysis

The plate is stained with iodine to indicate zones where the starch was cleared.

4.4 Screening for antimicrobial properties of study isolates

Test organisms	Mean of zones +- Standard error
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	10.31+-0.94 ^a
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	11.70+- 1.12 ^a
<i>Candida albicans</i>	11.31-+0.94 ^a
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	13.00-+1.12 ^a

Table 4.2: Means of zones of inhibition of test organisms against the isolates

Means with the same letters are not significantly different. F value (1.15) p value (0.330).

This means were obtained after two way ANOVA was carried out on the triplicate zones of inhibition. In all the isolates, at least one bacterial strain showed sensitivity to the metabolites.

Most of the microorganisms were inhibited by the metabolites.

Figure 4.2 zones of inhibition of clinical isolates against actinomycete isolates.

T1y and T5b had high inhibition zones. T5a had the least zones of inhibition. T1 was active against *Candida albicans*. T1y was active against *staphylococcus aureus*.

Plate 4: Zero zones of inhibition of T5a against *Bacillus subtilis*

T5a isolate was not active against *Bacillus subtilis* which is shown by the zero zones of inhibition. *Bacillus subtilis* was resistant to the metabolites produced by T5a isolate.

Plate 5: Zones of inhibition on T1y isolate against *Staphylococcus aureus*

Diffusion disks were used. 1 represents the negative control using sterile water and it had no zone of inhibition. Discs 2, 3 and 4 were the discs obtained from soaking of the filter discs in the supernatant recovered from T1y isolate which was then air dried and inoculated against clinical *Staphylococcus aureus* swabbed on nutrient agar. Disc 2, 3 and 4 had great zones of inhibition. T1y showed great antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

4.5 Positive control results using known antibiotics against test isolates incubated at 28°C

Antibiotic	symbol	Concentration (mcg)	<i>S.aureus</i> (mm)	<i>E.coli</i> (mm)	<i>B.subtilis</i> (mm)
Ampicillin	AMP	10	24	6	12
Chloromphenicol	C	30	30	28	6
Co-trimoxazole	COT	25	26	-	24
Penicillin -G	P	10	-	-	-13
Gentamycin	GEN	10	15	20	30
Ceftazidime	CAZ	30	-	14	

Amikacyin	AK	30	18	20	-
Cephtriaxone	C	30	-	-	8
Cefuroxime	CXM	30	-	12	-

Table 4.3: Antibiotic discs showing zones of inhibition against test microorganisms incubated at 28°C

Antibiotic discs. More than 19mm-susceptible, less than 13mm –resistant. Known antibiotics showed significant activity against the drug resistant isolates. However, resistance was also exhibited.

Plate 6: Positive control of chloramphenicol on *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Chloromphenicol was active against *Staphylococcus aureus* at 30 mm. this was the greatest zone of inhibition as compared to ampicillin, Gemtamycin and Amikyacin. This indicates that Chloromphenicol is effective against *Staphylococcus aureus* in comparison to other antibiotics.

Figure 4.3: Inhibition of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Chloromphenicol had a great zone of inhibition together with Co-trimoxazole. Gentamycin had the lowest zone of inhibition. Isolates T1y and T5b had high sensitivity against *staphylococcus aureus*. T1 and T5a had no zones of inhibition same as the negative control.

Figure 4.4: Inhibition of *E.coli*

Chloromphenicol is very active against *Escherichia coli* hence shows a great zone of inhibition. Isolate T1y and T5b had inhibitions relative to Gentamycin and Amikyacin. Ampicillin, T1y and isolate T5a had zero zones of inhibition indicating resistance.

Figure 4.5: Inhibition of *B.subtilis*

Isolate 5b had a great zone of inhibition only surpassed by known antibiotics Gentamycin and Co trimoxazole. Chloromphenicol had a small zone of inhibition together with isolate T5a and T4b.

CHAPTER 5. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 DISCUSSION

In this study, the colonies isolated from the upper and lower farms were not significantly different which is indicative that the soils were uniform in the upper and lower farms. The soils were intermediate and the farmers used organic manure. The soil organic content influences the population and type of actinomycetes with large numbers occurring in soils with large undecomposed organic material as documented by (Paul EA, 2006). The number of colonies was found to be lower in this study because of the Media used. Studies carried out using Casein Starch Agar and International Streptomycin Project (ISP-2) showed more colony counts as was found in a study by Russell, H (2012) The physical and biochemical characteristics in this study attested that the isolates were indeed actinomycetes as was the study carried by Pooja *et al* (2015) which can be attributed to isolation of similar actinomycetes. Out of the colonies obtained 8 were picked using biochemical characteristics to be screened for metabolites. The colonies utilize starch as their source of energy and carbon hence a large portion of clear zones when iodine is added to the plate. This differs with a previous study (Tebo et al., 2015). This can be attributed to the areas of study being different. Affirmations from Arya and Singh (2016), indicate that different actinomycetes have different carbon source requirements based on their metabolic pathways. The colonies are either white, yellow or pink with white being dominant. This agrees with a previous study carried out in Kericho (Rotich et al., 2017). Physio- chemical characteristics of soil could be behind these varying colony colours. In microscopy, the isolates were purple filaments and long rods. Actinomycetes are gram positive hence retain the purple colour of crystal violet. The disc well did not indicate any zones of inhibition. The diffusion discs showed zones of inhibition. Most isolates

are active against both gram positive and gram negative bacteria. The culture medium used influenced the zones of inhibition found. Studies where the use of Bennet media and Mueller Hinton were used indicated more antimicrobial activity against the test organisms both of which were not used in this study (Zerizer *et al.*, 2005). Out of the 7 actinomycetes identified, 4 were active against gram negative *Escherichia coli*. That is 66% of the metabolites are able to act against *E.coli*. 5 were active against *Candida* which is a yeast this represents about 71% of the total isolates. 5 isolates were active against gram positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. This represents 71% positivity rate. A 70% positivity rate was found against *Staphylococcus aureus* in a study carried out in Ethiopia (Mekkonen *et al.*, 2005) This result concurs with previous studies which showed that metabolites isolated from soil had activity against gram positive bacteria (Thakur *et al.*, 2007).According to BS Chadha *et al.*, (2011) about 38% of isolates from soils in India showed antimicrobial activity against test isolates such as *E.coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* which was Methicillin resistant. Mohan and Baskaran (2011), also documented that the highest antagonistic activities were against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*. In a different study, an isolate was active against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* but had no effect on *Escherichia coli* or *Candida albicans* (Dalin *et al.*, 2010), which coincides with this study of isolate T1y. Isolate T5b had the greatest zones of inhibition against all the isolates. Some of the isolates did not show any zones of inhibition. Isolates with the highest zones of inhibition indicate that the metabolites harvested were able to inhibit their growth and can therefore be used to control or stop the activity of the bacteria and yeast. Those isolates that had no zones of inhibition indicate that the bacteria and yeast were resistant to the metabolites produced or the metabolites did not have any effect on the microorganisms. Some of the isolates showed intermediate zones which indicates that the microorganisms were neither resistant nor very

susceptible to the metabolites. Gram positive bacteria were more susceptible to the metabolites as compared to gram negative bacteria. This is due to the difference in cell wall components, with gram negative bacteria having an outer membrane that is absent in gram positive bacteria this is also found in a study carried out in Saudi Arabia (Saleh *et al.*, 2014). *E. coli* is resistant to Ampicillin and Cefuroxime but very susceptible to chloramphenicol and amikaycin. The same findings have been reported by Galindo-Mendez (2020). *Bacillus* is resistant to amplicillin and chloramphenicol. It is however, very susceptible to Gentamycin as was also found by Ciffo F. (1984). *Staphylococcus aureus* is very susceptible to Chloramphenicol in this study, contrary to other studies that indicated that it was resistant to the antibiotic (Yang Z *et al.*, 2015). Other studies have documented that *Staphylococcus* is resistant to Penicillin (Nam HM *et al.*, 2011). Penicillin was not tested in this study against *Staphylococcus aureus*. Resistance to Ampicillin and Penicillin is attributed to the production of beta lactamase which inactivates the antibiotics (Green *et al.*, 2004), which was not the same as the result found in this study.

Numerous studies carried out on actinomycetes isolated from soil and antibacterial properties evaluated prove that this is an avenue for production of new antimicrobial agents. The results in this study also supports previous studies that soil actinomycetes are indeed capable of producing novel antibiotics.

5.2 CONCLUSION

The soils from Tharaka Nithi County have actinomycetes with metabolites that control bacterial pathogens. The metabolites had significant activity against the clinical microorganisms tested. The metabolites however, have to be purified in order to obtain compounds of clinical value. Further screening and identification of the specific species also have to be carried out using the 16sRNA method to correctly identify the isolates. Actinomycetes are not restricted to soil and can be found

in other ecological niches which when explored can be good sources of bioactive metabolites. This bioactive metabolites will help combat the problem of multi drug resistance.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

From this study, it is recommended that; the soil ecological niche in Tharaka Nithi County be explored more to obtain actinomycetes that produce metabolites which contain antimicrobial properties.

Secondly, that the government increases the funding of scientific and clinical research so as to arrive at solutions on multidrug resistance.

REFERENCES

- Bizuye, A., Bii, C., Erastus, G., & Maina, N. (2017). Antibacterial metabolite prospecting from Actinomycetes isolated from waste damped soils from Thika, central part of Kenya. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Disease*, 7(12), 757-764.
- Chaudhary, H. S., Soni, B., Shrivastava, A. R., & Shrivastava, S. (2013). Diversity and versatility of actinomycetes and its role in antibiotic production. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 3(8), S83-S94.
- Chopra, A., & Ra, I. (1996). *Understanding antibacterial action and resistance*: Ellis Horwood Limited, London, United Kingdom.
- Craveri, R., Hill, L., Manachini, P., & Silvestri, L. (1965). Deoxyribonucleic acid base compositions among thermophilic actinomycetes: the occurrence of two strains with low GC content. *Microbiology*, 41(3), 335-339.
- Emerson, R., Whiffen, A. J., Bohonos, N., & Deboer, C. (1946). Studies on the production of antibiotics by actinomycetes and molds. *Journal of bacteriology*, 52(3), 357.
- Genilloud, O. (2017). Actinomycetes: still a source of novel antibiotics. *Natural product reports*, 34(10), 1203-1232.
- Gerber, N., & Lechevalier, H. (1965). Geosmin, an earthy-smelling substance isolated from actinomycetes. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 13(6), 935-938.
- Jamdhade, V. (2019). Antibiotic production of penicillin.
- Kanazawa, S., & Filip, Z. (1986). Distribution of microorganisms, total biomass, and enzyme activities in different particles of brown soil. *Microbial Ecology*, 12(2), 205-215.
- Mahajan, G. B., & Balachandran, L. (2012). Antibacterial agents from actinomycetes—a review. *Front Biosci (Elite Ed)*, 4(4), 240-253.

- Marshall, K., & Alexander, M. (1960). Growth characteristics of fungi and actinomycete *Journal of bacteriology*, 80(3), 412.
- Masand, A., Kumar, N., & Patial, V. (2015). Actinomycosis (lumpy jaw) in cow: a case report. *Comparative Clinical Pathology*, 24(3), 541-543.
- McArthur, A. G., Waglechner, N., Nizam, F., Yan, A., Azad, M. A., Baylay, A. J., . . . Ejim, L. (2013). The comprehensive antibiotic resistance database. *Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy*, 57(7), 3348-3357.
- Nichols, D. E., & Herrell, W. E. (1948). Penicillin in the treatment of actinomycosis. *The Journal of laboratory and clinical medicine*, 33(5), 521-525.
- Sarma, M., Dangi, P., & Choudhary, M. (2014). Actinomycetes: source, identification, and their applications. *Int J Curr Microbiol App Sci*, 3(2), 801-832.
- Smego Jr, R. A., & Foglia, G. (1998). Actinomycosis. *Clinical infectious diseases*, 1255-1261.
- White, R. J. (2012). The early history of antibiotic discovery: empiricism ruled. In *Antibiotic Discovery and Development* (pp. 3-31): Springer.
- Berdy J. *Bioactive microbial metabolites*. J Antibiot.2005;58 (1)1-26
- Penicillin in the treatment of actinomycosis. *The Journal of laboratory and clinical medicine*.
- Sujatha P, Swethalatha P. *isolation, screening and characterization of antibiotic producing actinomycetes* from Kapuluppada plastic waste dumping yard, Vishakhapataman. Int J Pharm Sci 2016; 8:221-9.
- Galindo-Méndez, M. (2020). Antimicrobial Resistance in Escherichia coli. In *E. coli Infection*. IntechOpen.

Negi, H., Rani, A., Joshi, S., & Sharma, P. K. (2020). Biodiversity of Microbial Community: Association with Sustainable Hill Agroecosystems. In *Microbiological Advancements for Higher Altitude Agro-Ecosystems & Sustainability* (pp. 163-181). Springer, Singapore.

Baskaran, R., Thenmozhi, S., Kumar, K. V., Mohan, P. M., & Vijayakumar, R. *Malaysian Journal of Microbiology*.

Sharma, D., Kaur, T., Chadha, B. S., & Manhas, R. K. (2011). Antimicrobial activity of actinomycetes against multidrug resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E. coli* and various other pathogens. *Tropical journal of pharmaceutical research*, 10(6), 801-808.

APPENDICES

M1 media preparation

250ml

Starch 2.0g

Peptone 0.5g

Agar 5g

Yeast 1g

Water 250ml